

Economic Recovery after a Financial Crisis

Part I

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Forewords

A company that has been affected by a reasonable period of inactivity due to a disaster, whether it be of calamity, war or a terrible global economic situation, has in its resumption of observing certain requirements not only of a financial but also a labor nature.

Leadership and decision-making is of the utmost importance for a positive recovery.

I -

Borrowing Money from a Bank

Long-term capital is secured by the sale of obligations such as bonds. Another portion of long-term capital is secured by the contribution of the owners when they buy stock. But in addition, there is the current working capital required to meet the non-coincidence of income and outgoing.

- Short-term borrowing. A banker is thought by many people to be a rather cold-blooded individual who is interested in nothing but the safety of his loan. In part, this is true, for it is his duty to safeguard the funds entrusted to him by others.

A banker will also look, except in the case of an extremely large corporation, at the personnel and their personalities. He is interested in their characters, as to whether or not they are honest. He is interested, obviously, in health, for if people are not expected to live very much longer, they may not be particularly good risks.

For this same reason he is interested in age. He is interested in training and natural talent of the applicants, which is an indication of their ability to run the business successfully. He is interested in their application; how hard do they work at their job?

External factors are just as important as the personal factors in granting loans. External factors include:

- Position of the business cycle;
- Development of the industry;
- Territorial conditions.

Obviously, during a recession it is much more difficult to get a loan than when business is good. It may be argued that this is not justice, but it cannot be denied that even in so prosaic a business as making loans, psychology plays a part. When a banker is convinced that everything is "going to the dogs," he is not particularly apt to be in a loan-granting mood.

On the other hand, even if there is no justification for his optimism, if everything looks good, the banker will be much freer in granting a loan, as there is a greater opportunity of getting the money back when things are good than when things are bad.

A banker is not too much interested in granting a loan to an entirely new industry—something which is not completely understood because he has no standards by which he can compare and determine the relative risk of the situation.

A loan to a company organized to remove gold from sea water would probably be refused. By the same token, a banker is not particularly interested in businesses which are in competition with long-established ventures.

A loan to help someone compete with a big Corporation would not interest the average banker; he would not feel that the business had much chance of success.

A business that is well understood and which has many small units in it is more apt to receive a loan because in this case the bank has many standards of comparison. Consequently, the bank is in a much better position to determine the suitability of making a loan.

Loans made to garment trades, power laundries, retail stores, and small manufacturers are relatively easy to justify.

A territory that has been devastated by earthquake or the ravages of war is not so good a risk as territory which is in good condition.

A territory that is completely dependent upon an industry which has failed or is temporarily in eclipse is not considered a good risk.

Property resources must be considered by the banker. Despite the discussion of the importance of the character of the personnel and the business conditions, the banker will always require written evidence as to the condition of the business.

Such written evidence consists of statements prepared by the firm, showing not only the balance sheet but also the profit and loss statement. Assets are of little value if the company cannot employ them to make a profit; so, a wise banker is not only interested in what the business seems to be worth but also in what it is able to earn.

These two financial statements are most important considerations in granting a loan. The banker will also draw upon reports from other banks, if available, on this particular business. He may also gather some information from trade associations.

At the European Union after the pandemic that close in layoff many businesses the bank will borrow money but there is the State warranty. That means that the bank is always safe to receive the money but the manager is personally debtor from the State that can execute its own wealth.

II -

Definition of Responsibility, Authority, and Accountability for Each Executive Position

Provision must be made for the clear written definition of responsibility, authority, and accountability for each executive position at a minimum. This is not automatically understood or properly implemented in many companies.

Not all managers know whom they report to or are sure who reports to them. The manager reports to its three bosses. This cannot possibly promote organizational harmony and a strong esprit de corps.

Some managers forget there is an organization structure in dealing with subordinates. While this can be justifiable in rare situations of expediency or emergency, it is an undesirable habit to get into because it undermines the authority and reduces the effectiveness of subordinate managers. In one such situation, the chief union representative made it a point to visit the company president with a grievance.

The president promptly resolved the grievance in the union favour without checking first with the foreman, superintendent, or industrial relations manager. That company ended up with more than a thousand formal, written, unresolved grievances because the chief executive bypassed the formal lines of authority.

And this single act virtually destroyed the morale of the first-line supervisors. Top executives must exercise control through attention to policy matters and problems of exceptional importance rather than through review of or interference with routine matters.

Defining and measuring organizational climate can be an elusive exercise. If management recognizes that there is competition between companies at the level of creative innovation in all business functions, it will program for and properly manage change in order to stay on top. Organizations must create changes in their environment and not merely adapt to them under pressure.

The very first requirement in overcoming obstacles to successful management of change is a determination to grow. Given this determination, management will recognize the price that must be paid and will willingly commit funds for growth. If top management establishes a climate of growth and encourages lower-level managers to develop, innovate, and expand their thinking, the company will grow instead of being content with routine day-to-day administration and improvements in operating efficiency.

To translate thinking into action requires planning and may require a full-time business planner. The organization must constantly reshape its objectives and work at building a favourable attitudinal climate for growth and change.

The organization attention to its external environment must be strong and systematic. Too often organizations devote a disproportionate amount of time to an analysis of what goes on inside the company.

Organizational climate is not built entirely on internal factors, but is significantly affected by the external environment-competition, growth opportunities, distribution patterns, transportation costs, legislation, technological trends, changing customer requirements, socioeconomic changes.

Paying close attention to these factors poises an organization for movement when the time becomes ripe. It stimulates internal climate improvement and pride in a forward-thinking company.

Once plans are devised to deal with major issues and major opportunities in the external environment they must be implemented. This may require pooling of talent and providing for necessary checks and balances. Information organization and flow must be developed. It may be necessary for tomorrow's business manager to completely restructure and reshape his organization to cope with modern society.

This takes a great deal of courage and capacity. It takes superior people who must be developed over a period of years. Good organizational climate does not come about by accident; it is the result of good planning and careful implementation.

III -

Formulation of Human Resources Strategy

The formulation of the organization's human resources strategy begins with basic questions concerning how employment will be structured, what corporate culture will be fostered, how careers will unfold in the organization, what sort of employees will be sought, and so forth.

Within this general category of tasks we include both organization-wide human resources strategy and the tailoring of that strategy to specific business units, regional units, functions, or divisions.

Especially important in terms of organization-wide strategy are answers to the questions: How consistent should human resources policies and practices be throughout the enterprise? Where are distinctions in policies and practices (across locales or employee subgroups) desirable? How much latitude should particular organizational units be given in formulating their own human resources strategies?

After the broad outlines of strategy have been set, questions about general policies arise, such as: What will be the broad base of compensation and performance management throughout the organization or in particular units? What tasks will be outsourced, and will the outsourcing be done via labour contractors or independent contractors?

What training will be done in-house, and what will be outsourced, and to whom? It is hard to draw a line between strategy and policy, and we will not make any attempt to do so: In this category we will include any human resources related activity that sets rules for the management of human resources that apply broadly to groups of employees.

Formulating strategy and general policies, it seems to us, is a managerial task of the utmost importance. It is fraught with ambiguity; there is no checklist of what to do or what to think about. The outcomes are noisy-how do you know if you've succeeded? Results often take a long time to be realized. Interdependencies with other parts of business strategy are tight.

At the same time, dependence on local environmental conditions can be important, so the local environment must be well understood by those who formulate human resources strategy and policies.

Finally, the tasks here strongly mix guardian and star elements. Poorly aligned or inconsistent human resources policies and practices can be devastating for an organization. At the same time, the ability to see beyond conventional wisdom, to put together a human resources system that works especially well, is as potent a competitive weapon as one can imagine.

- Implementation of Strategy and Policies. In this category we have in mind tasks that involve nontrivial judgment in fitting general policies and procedures to specific cases.

Performance evaluation of individuals and teams, crafting job designs, decisions on whom to hire (and where specifically to look, although this could be construed as part

of policy formation), decisions on whom to promote, decisions on training for individuals, specific layoff decisions, and the like all fit here.

Ambiguity in these tasks is not particularly high if a well-formed set of human resources policies and practices is in place; however, outcomes are noisy and feedback can be substantially delayed.

Interdependencies with other parts of the business can be substantial; decision-makers should have a fairly well-developed "big picture" of the organization or, at least, of the specific function involved. Because of reputation and social comparison effects, these tasks are predominately guardian roles, although especially when it comes to recognition of talent and accurate placement of individuals, some star aspects are involved.

- Record Keeping, Compliance, and Personnel Service Delivery. Here we have in mind those tasks that, unfortunately, have come to dominate many line managers' perceptions of what the human resources Department does: compliance reports; keeping employee records; filling out forms for benefits and payroll; and so forth, on down to buying the beverages and pizza for the regularly scheduled employee beer blast.

There isn't a lot of ambiguity here and performance is fairly easily monitored. The job is a mix of some guardian and mainly foot-soldier tasks: Screwing up compliance reports can get the firm in trouble with legal authorities, and a bad benefits office can reduce employee morale pretty quickly, but management that isn't completely asleep or complacent can usually avoid the big disasters in this realm.

This enumeration of the tasks involved in doing human resources management helps clarify a root problem with how human resources is traditionally organized. In the traditional organization, this bundles together all these tasks, a small fraction of the activities account for a huge proportion of the value added by the function, by creating potential upside and/or helping the organization avoid downside disasters. In contrast, most of the activities conducted, measured by time expended or paper consumed, are the routine foot-soldier tasks, perceived as adding little value by managers and employees.

Complying with rules and filling out forms imposed by central human resources regarding job searches, performance appraisal, or compensation and benefits - or being required to have a human resources representative present during a sensitive conference with a subordinate are frequently not viewed as helping matters very much.

And employees, once they are hired, often interact with the human resources department only when they have a problem or concern, so they may not have an especially positive view of the function either.

In any event, it is not altogether surprising that a function that is perceived as responsible for explaining benefits programs, processing change-of-address forms, complying with governmental regulations, and enforcing policies that limit managers' discretion on how they can treat employees-or that is touted as the "conscience" or "kinder, gentler side" of the corporation-is unlikely to be viewed as a hard-charging, tough-minded, strategic business partner.

In addition it's easier to measure how well the human resources department is doing in terms of filling out forms and delivering routine services; it's a lot harder to measure how well it does at formulating and implementing a human resources strategy.

IV -

Fundamentals of Institutional Behaviour

The pivotal factors which determine the nature and speed of an organization response to environmental change are the perceptions of administrators and the choices they make in key areas.

In a very real sense, administrators enact or create the environment to which the organization responds.

- They do so, first, by scanning those areas of the environment which they deem to be important.

- They also perform the initial interpretation of information about the environment which forms the basis for subsequent actions by other members of the organization.

- Administrators determine which distinctive competences will be developed by the organization - that is, what unique configuration of special capabilities and skills the organization will employ in attempting to arrive at an acceptable equilibrium with its chosen environment.

It can be argued that the administrative system is continually responsible for solving three broad sets of problems, one or more of which may be particularly salient at any given point in the organization evolution. These problems are:

- (1) The entrepreneurial problem - selecting a viable product - market domain and a set of performance objectives relative to that domain;

- (2) The engineering problem - creating a technological process for servicing the selected domain; and

(3) The administrative problem - developing an organizational structure to coordinate and control the technology and, further, to direct those entrepreneurial activities perceived as necessary for maintaining the organization future continuity.

Each of these problems is interrelated. Faced with a major decline in the markets for their products, many of the manufacturers of goods were simply forced out of business.

Those who solved the entrepreneurial problem, however, by going into different product and market areas were met with two new sets of problems: how to create and distribute these new products (the engineering problem) and how to structure, direct, and control their reconstituted organizations (the administrative problem).

The entrepreneurial problem, however, is not necessarily the precursor of the engineering and administrative problems. The development of a new technological capability and/ or capacity may create a new entrepreneurial opportunity. Purchasing a specialized line of equipment generally unavailable within the industry, it is possible to enter markets for which products would have been too expensive. Or, alternatively, outdated solutions to the administrative problem may lead to an entrepreneurial problem, and so on.

In an ongoing organization, administrators should be aware that they are responsible for solving each of these three problems, in many instances almost simultaneously.

Solving the administrative problem, however, involves more than simply rationalizing the system already developed (uncertainty reduction); it also involves formulating and implementing the processes which will enable the organization to continue to evolve (uncertainty exploration).

In the ideal organization, administrators would be equally adept at performing two somewhat conflicting functions: They would be able to create an administrative system (structure and processes) that could smoothly direct and monitor the organization current activities without, at the same time, allowing the system to become so ingrained that future activities were jeopardized.

Such a perspective requires the administrative system to be viewed as both a lagging and leading variable in the process of adaptation.

- As a lagging variable, the administrative system must rationalize, through the development of appropriate structures and processes, the strategic decisions made at previous points in the adjustment process.

- As a leading variable, on the other hand, the administrative system will facilitate or restrict the organization future capacity to adapt depending on the extent to which top

management articulates and reinforces the paths along which such activity can proceed.

Administration is the key ingredient in one of man's most impressive social inventions, the work organization.

Over the ages, many of our most ambitious undertakings, from pyramids to space exploration, have been achieved only through the combined output of complex assemblages of human, physical, and financial resources.

The process of accumulating, organizing, applying, and maintaining these resources for current and emergent organizational goals are, in a word, administration. And, just as organizations are among man's most notable inventions, administration is one of man's most challenging tasks.

The challenge of administration is not simply the complexity of the process but rather the fact that the administrative "problem" is never completely solved. The variables involved-both external and internal to the organization-are frequently changing, and each change places new or different demands on the administrative process.

Moreover, the effectiveness of the administrative process must be judged not only in terms of current performance but also in terms of the extent to which today's administrative actions facilitate future organizational performance. That is, an administrative action which may be effective in meeting current organizational needs but which restricts the adaptive of organizational resources to upcoming needs may be judged, on balance, ineffective.

It must already be apparent that defining administration broadly. **The term administration is frequently used in conjunction with, and sometimes as a substitute for, a number of other terms, most prominently "leadership" and management.**

In both theory and research, leadership is most often concerned with face to - face interaction among individuals of differing status (although leadership acts among peers are gaining increased attention).

The key characteristic of leadership is personal action aimed at influencing the behaviour of some particular individual or group. Management, on the other hand, entails the direction and coordination not only of people but also of physical and financial resources toward a given set of organizational goals.

These goals, in turn, have been defined by top management as part of an ongoing process of relating the organization to its environment. Involving more than face-to-face interactions, management includes searching the environment for change and opportunity, reducing uncertainty for the rest of the organization by defining tasks and goals, and creating a structure of roles and work processes to ensure the efficient

utilization of resources. Thus, unlike leadership, management is also concerned with relationships between and among organizations and with the larger environment.

Although the term management tends to be used more in the private sector while the term administration tends to be associated with the public sector, we see no theoretical or practical benefits to be gained from distinguishing between the two terms. Therefore, management and administration are used interchangeably to refer to the set of decisions, actions, and mechanisms required defining, developing, and maintaining the alignment of the total organization with its environment.

Concern with administration is, of course, nothing new. Almost from the beginning of recorded history, heads of organizations have proclaimed the problems of administration and presented their own solutions.

In earlier periods, these problems were primarily limited to public organizations: **the state, the military, and the church.**

The emergence of large-scale commercial enterprises over the past several hundred years has now brought the private sectors management problems into full view. In both arenas, however, parallel searches for administrative effectiveness has been numerous and prolonged.

The first target of the search for administrative effectiveness was personal characteristics. Plato sought to overcome scarcity by breeding and training a special caste of philosopher-kings; and Machiavelli claimed that insight, guile, and single-mindedness were the key characteristics of the successful administrator.

Adopting this same approach, behavioural scientists throughout the present century have pursued an elusive set of characteristics which might identify the ideal administrator. Despite these sustained efforts, however, neither physical nor personality attributes have proved to be predictive of administrative excellence.

Over a similarly lengthy time period, another investigation has been underway to find the ideal administrative structure and process. Jethro advised Moses to delegate judgment (administration) over the tens and hundreds and thousands lest the Israelites wander forever in the wilderness; and a thousand or so years later, the Roman legions marched across the Mediterranean world and into Europe with an army structured on similar lines.

Over the past hundred years, scholars have studied these two hallmarks of organization design, along with the governance of the Catholic Church, the evolution of the military general staff, the development of the modern governmental bureau and countless other organizations in search of a reliable set of administrative laws or principles.

However, ideal principles, structures, and processes, like ideal personal characteristics, have also proved vulnerable to the vagaries of time and circumstance-administrative structures and policies which appeared highly effective in one organization and period have frequently failed in other organizations and under other conditions.

Viewed historically, the search for the ideal personal and structural characteristics of effective administration has failed to provide many lasting answers but has succeeded in clarifying the proper questions to be asked.

Today, most scholars no longer seek the one best solution to all administrative problems. Instead, the bywords of modern theorists are systems and contingency. Systems analysts portray the organization as a total system, composed of many interrelated parts, that must respond to a wide range of external (markets, suppliers, etc. - and internal - technologies, personalities, etc. - demands.

Contingency theorists, in turn, seek to discover the conditions under which various organizational systems are most effective-that is, when the organization is most fully meeting both the demands of the environment and the needs of its members.

It is not clear at this point whether modern theorists, guided by the systems and contingency concepts, have brought us significantly closer to the truth about administration than their predecessors. What is clear, in retrospect, is that few of today's answers will be perfectly suitable for tomorrow's administrative questions.

A -

General Model of Administration

The administrative process is influenced by characteristics of the organization itself and the people within it, both of which in turn are shaped by the broader environment from which they are drawn.

There are major organization variables: the **basic goals and tasks** of the organization (product line, markets to be served, etc.); the **technology** for creating and delivering the organization's product or services (work layout, production processes, etc.); and the **structure of departments and roles** required to coordinate and control the technology.

Over time, these organization variables tend to take on an identity of their own, apart from the administrators who created and developed them. Most of us would be willing to make some predictions about the administrative problems and processes of an organization knowing nothing more than its basic goals, technology, and structure. At the very least, we would be willing to bet that the manner in which the administrative role was performed would be quite different in a research and development laboratory, a bank, and an public service.

The relationship between organization variables and the administrative process is interactive. It would appear that if administrators can create the organization's goals, technology, and structure, then certainly they should be able to modify each of these variables in response to perceived changes in the organization's environment.

However, in most mature organizations, such internal changes are likely to be marginal, except in the face of major environment shifts such as a dramatic change in resource availability, or population trends. In fact, even when confronted with major environmental changes, administrators may perceive some organization variables to be relatively intractable.

Human Variables - The administrative process is also influenced and constrained by a set of people variables: the abilities, attitudes, and personalities of organization members. These characteristics are affected by the environment from which organization members are drawn, and, in the short run, they too are difficult to change.

Over time-and within limits-members skills can be upgraded; attitudes can be influenced; and age, sex, and racial proportions can be modified. However, at any given time, administrators must deal with what basically exists within the human subsystem while attempting changes at the margin. Here again, knowing nothing more than the characteristics of organization members, we might be tempted to make guesses about the conduct of administration. We would, for example, expect a hospital administrator to deal with his medical staff differently than with his office personnel.

Integrative Mechanisms - The administrator is both powerful and impotent. When he sets organizational goals or changes structure, the administrator is wielding power unavailable to other members of the organization. But having done so, he is then at the mercy of these decisions.

That is, once people and processes are in place, major alterations of these variables are achieved only at a high cost. Consequently, an administrator who is intent upon obtaining an effective integration of organization and human variables should be aware of the range of alternatives available to him in performing this task.

B -

Planning and Direction of an Organization

With regard to planning and direction, administrative behaviour might range

I. From unilateral determination of plans, policies, and objectives to joint determination with those individuals affected

2. From close and direct supervision (either in person or through detailed procedures and reports) to general, supportive supervision which allows broad self-direction and self-control to be exercised in the pursuit of agreed-upon objectives

C -

Organization and Job Design

Alternatives available in utilizing these mechanisms might range

1. **From structures** which arrange groups of functional specialists in traditional hierarchical layers to more loosely linked, self-paced teams with heterogeneous skills grouped around a product, part, or integrated stage of the process
2. **From job designs** emphasizing highly specialized and segmented collections of tasks to designs which attempt to encompass a meaningful range of activities into self-paced, self-evaluated operations

Selection and Training – Appraisal and Development

For these mechanisms, alternatives might range

1. From selection and training processes which focus on presumed traits and abilities associated with immediate job requirements to more flexible systems which attempt to balance the long-run needs of the organization and the individual
2. From superior-conducted appraisal based on standard characteristics and behaviours to joint appraisal (superior/subordinates) focused on progress toward previously agreed-upon job targets or objectives
3. From unilaterally planned and directed development programs to flexible procedures where organization members are included in the process of setting their own development goals and choosing the means of achieving them

Communication and Control

Here, alternatives might range

- I. From **communications systems** which primarily provide for downward flows of orders and instructions and upward flows of reports to information systems designed

to provide operating units with access to all the data they feel are necessary to their performance

2. From **control systems** which collect progress information from operating units for transmission to distant evaluation points to short feedback loop designs which allow operating units to immediately appraise and adjust their own performance

Reward Systems

Within reward systems, alternatives might range

1. From systems built exclusively around either longevity or merit alone to more flexible systems which acknowledge both loyalty and performance

2. From unilateral determination of rewards and the method of their attainment to systems in which organization members have a voice in determining the nature of rewards and the paths by which these can be achieved.

The extent to which choices among the integrative mechanisms take into account the particular set of organizational and people characteristics of a given system determines whether or not these mechanisms will be integrative, or, if you will, disintegrative.

For example, the approach to planning and direction which works well in a savings bank might prove both disruptive and ineffective in a land-development company staffed with a variety of professionals putting together complex land and housing projects. This does not mean that human and organization variables determine - or should determine - administrative decisions and actions.

Rather, these variables should be viewed as constraints within which administrative choices must be made and, subsequently, as likely to be either enhanced or diminished given the choice of a particular set of integrative devices.

D -

Organizational Structure Innovation

Organizational planning will always remain a major management function. The need for effectively functioning organizations is too important to leave planning to organization specialists alone.

This statement is in no sense a forecast of a decline in the number of organization departments in the corporations. On the contrary, the growth in the numbers of organization specialists is expected to be rather impressive in the next five years. This

is because operating managers, who will continue to be primarily concerned with and responsible for implementing organization plans, will rely more and more on the staff specialist for advice, guidance, and innovation.

Organization planning functions tend to come about when organizations are faced with massive growth or change or increased complexity. And all indications point toward an increasingly complex environment, both in the business community and in society at large; and, thus, organizations will need an increasingly complex set of rules to carry out their missions.

The increase in governmental regulations and in special interest groups and the changing aspirations and expectations of employees suggest a future need for different ways of accomplishing organizational objectives.

In the years ahead, the tried and true maxims about organizations will change. Many organizations have already developed group chief executive offices. Often, one man can no longer oversee the operation of very complex structures.

The nature of the marketplace and the development of knowledgeable workers have changed the definition of functional positions.

The organization specialist will perform several functions within the organization, but service to the operating manager will be paramount. Services provided in all areas of the planning process (structural analysis, power analysis, job definition, and staffing) will fall into at least three areas: advice, innovation, and research.

The operating manager must implement changes. The role of the specialist will be to suggest needed changes based on analysis, aid in the development of implementation procedures, and evaluate the effectiveness of procedures.

One study points out that the successful organization executive does not deal in ivory tower visions of organizational life but gives realistic advice useful to the practicing manager.

The organization planning group is often the one group within the company that concerns itself with finding new ways to manage people, identify potential leaders, and divide work to meet the needs of the company.

The effectiveness of the group will depend in large part on its continued ability to innovate.

Much of the work of the organization planning group will be research oriented. Analysis of behaviour, power relationships, and production systems will be the key to the group charter.

Few operating managers today want to make major organizational decisions based on hunches or ideas that may have worked in the past or in other situations. Research in organization, culture, market strategies, production techniques, and management processes will be one of the cornerstones that will insure continued effectiveness.

The effective organization planning group will be able to measure its contribution to the organization in several ways. Its contribution will be evident in increases in operational effectiveness, the end of the problem that brought organizational planning into existence, lower production and administrative expenses, better relationships between operating departments, the selection of better people for key positions, and the creation of a ready reserve of employees for jobs that had not been designed when the group was initiated.

Organizational planning can easily result in little or no improvement in performance if not implemented effectively. **Successful implementation involves several elements:**

- **Communication,**
- **Management information systems,**
- **Policies and procedures,**
- **Timing, and**
- **Compensation.**

There is more to the communication of organizational changes than the distribution of corporate announcements to the newspapers. The manner in which they are made known to the members of the organization is crucial to success.

Whenever changes occur, chain reactions are set up that affect large groups of people. Relationships change; objectives change; status changes; power is redistributed. People affected must have a thorough understanding not only of changes but the reasons for them.

Time and again, organizational changes developed for valid reasons achieve nothing.

The way that information is processed within an organization changes when the organization changes. Yet, provision for different reporting relationships is often made after changes are already implemented.

As the objectives of jobs change and the individual objectives of managers change, the way in which financial data are reported internally also changes. For instance consider the company that traditionally measured its progress by volume of sales. When the company was reorganized and new objectives initiated, a key measure of progress-and, in fact, the way that employees would be compensated-was gross profit on sales.

It was soon determined that the reporting systems in use for several years would not accommodate new report needs.

A new system was developed but could not be implemented until several months had passed.

When changes are made in the structure, job design, power allocations, and staffing of an organization, they should be documented. Many organizations make the mistake of leaving the development of policies and procedures that back up organization changes until there is less disruption within the affected groups. But, in fact, the faster that policies and procedures can be distributed, read, and understood, the better.

E -

Organization Strategic Planning

Organization planning is an attempt by a manager, with or without the assistance of a resource consultant, to improve the performance of an organization by systematically analyzing and, if indicated, changing one or more of four basic organizational elements:

- (1) The fundamental structure;
- (2) The design of positions;
- (3) The allocation of power;
- (4) The staffing of key positions in the organization.

Any top manager can become a more effective organization planner. In fact, the top manager in any organization is the only one who can make the critical decisions necessary to think through an organizational plan and implement it.

The top manager is fortunate if he has a fellow manager, either line or staff, who can help-perhaps just to act as a sounding board or a devil advocate, or simply to lend a sympathetic ear. In any event, for the organization plan to have a chance of success it must represent the convictions, experience, commitment, and judgment of the manager responsible for obtaining results from that grouping of people he calls his organization.

An effective organization planner can anticipate with reasonable accuracy how the organization will perform in response to changes that are made in any of the four elements identified in the definition of organization planning.

Realistic and patient implementation of plans is as important in this view as the planning process itself.

These should be stated at the outset:

1. **There are no rules of organization.** If someone's mind is fixed on absolute notions of span of control, an appropriate number of levels from top to bottom in an organization, complete preference for profit centre organization, an absolute aversion to task force management, or any other methodology or dogma of organization, it will have difficulty in improving his effectiveness as an organization planner. There is no universal set of rules.

2. **Personality factors obviously must be considered in organization planning.** That is, the personalities of individuals holding key positions that affect the direction of the organization must be taken into account in planning. Modelling organization decisions to accommodate personality strengths and / or weaknesses should be done reluctantly and only after a thorough analysis and recognition of the trade-offs involved in such compromises.

3. **Changing structure is the most disruptive of all actions** that an organization planner (i.e., a responsible manager) can take. Managers often have unrealistic expectations of the short-term impact of structural changes. Time and patience are needed to see the impact of any structural change of significance.

4. **Proper structure facilitates organization performance,** but it in no way guarantees success. Conversely, improper structures can, and many do, function reasonably well. However, improper structure is an impediment to full effectiveness.

5. **All aspects of organization planning** (structuring, designing positions, managing power, and staffing) must be approached from the point of view of what the top manager in the organization is trying to accomplish. What are his short- and long-range objectives?

6. Most if not all controversy over the issue of **decentralization versus centralization** and the conflict in line and staff relationships results from management power plays.

7. Probably because of its emotional overtones and its potential to cause conflict, the most neglected aspect of organization planning is the systematic analysis and management of **power allocation.**

8. Invariably all the benefits to be gained from a well-planned organization (in the areas of structure, staffing, position and design, and power allocation) cannot be gained at the same time. The top manager must make trade-offs to get the optimum balance of benefits from these elements. The trade-offs can be made systematically only when their impact on obtaining objectives and overcoming obstacles is accurately perceived.

9. Work, or activity that passes for work, will expand to fill time all given objective.

Systematic job design to provide a full challenge and a full workload directed towards the objectives of the organization are a must. Enforcing that design, where necessary, cannot be avoided.

10. There is a clear advantage to involving in planning those individuals who will be vitally affected by any changes resulting from the organizational planning process.

11. Organization planning is not a science, but it is certainly more than a seat of the pants art. Principles and processes have led to significant improvements in the ability of many managers to enhance the effectiveness of their organizations.

Organizational Adjustment

Organizational performance may decline for reasons other than top management neglect of either the leading or lagging aspects of the administrative role. A change in overall economic conditions or any other force not entirely controllable by management may require adjustments to be made by the organization.

Since the demands for adjustment which stem from sources both external and internal to the organization-are numerous, complex, and vary in predictability, management must necessarily choose to focus on some demands more than others.

Put simply, **strategy is a characteristic way of responding to conditions in the environment, and several different strategies may be equally viable in a generally similar environment.** For example, in the college textbook publishing industry, some organizations elect to remain in very narrow product-market domains which they attempt to serve with maximum efficiency.

Conversely, other companies continually shift their domains, emphasizing new areas of product or services and market opportunity as rapidly as management can accurately identify them. Between these two extremes lie other feasible strategies.

Successful organizations appear to have achieved a close fit between strategy and structure (a broad term encompassing a variety of organizational characteristics such as technology, distinctive competence, etc.).

Moreover, strategy and structure tend to reinforce each other as the organization evolves. For example, an organization whose strategy is to hold its product market domain relatively constant while improving manufacturing capacity and efficiency will invest its managerial and financial resources differently than an organization that is attempting to develop new markets and products.

Management of the former organization will be more likely to promote individuals with production or engineering backgrounds into key executive slots and to provide these administrators with the necessary resources.

These administrators, in turn, will attempt to shape the organization along the lines of their own expertise, and, of course, they also have a vested interest in maintaining the strategy that was responsible for their arrival in these positions.

Thus, over time, organizations become more adept at dealing with certain kinds of environmental demands than others.

The demands for organizational adjustment are by now undoubtedly familiar to most administrators: external demands for higher standards, lower costs, adaptability, and flexibility appear to be colliding with internal demands for more meaningful and responsible work assignments, particularly among the younger members of the work force.

To some administrators, these two sources of stress on the administrative system appear to be merely additive - they sum up to the inevitable problems of ever-increasing organizational size.

To a growing number of organization leaders, however, these external and internal demands are being viewed as complementary rather than conflicting. For these administrators, the quest is to develop administrative processes that more fully utilize the full range of capabilities of organization members, thus satisfying their needs while enlarging the organization's capacity to respond to external demands for higher quality and increased flexibility.

Such a quest is obviously neither simple nor short. Instead, it is only likely to be accomplished through a continuous learning program within the organization. Long-term programs for learning and change have been emerging in recent years under the heading of Organization Development.

F -

Behavioural Approach to Administration

In recent years human problems and concerns have taken precedence over other societal pressures. For many years technology had dominated. Now it is generally acknowledged that the pendulum of technology has swung too far out of balance with more basic human concerns. In the so-called future-shock type of environment that exists today, society is no longer asking what technology can do but instead what it should be allowed to do.

The new societal mood is translated into a reordering of priorities.

Generally recognized goals today include improving the quality of life; providing equal opportunities regardless of colour or sex; and eliminating wars, accidents, disease, and poverty. On the other hand, landing a person on Mars, building supersonic transports, and making more effective nuclear weapons are of secondary importance to most people.

The new preoccupation with human concerns in society has filtered down into the organization as well. Social issues such as environmental protection, equal rights, and consumerism are of vital concern for all of today organizations.

However, besides the social responsibilities, there is a realization on the part of most modern administrators of the importance of what Douglas McGregor labelled the human, as opposed to the technical, side of enterprise.

Much publicity has recently been given to blue-collar blues and white-collar woes. Newspaper stories with headlines such as the following are becoming increasingly common.

The behavioural approach to administration is usually viewed as beginning with the Hawthorne studies in the late 1920 and early 1930. These historically significant studies marked the first time that human behaviour in organizations was systematically analyzed.

The scientific management movement recognized the human element of business. Scientific managers did not give as much attention to the systematic analysis of the human element as they did to the physical mechanical aspects of work. It was not until the Hawthorne studies that the powerful dynamics of interpersonal relationships in organizations were recognized and documented.

Studies showed that preadolescent boys overwhelmingly preferred a democratic leader over either an authoritarian or laissez-faire leader. Another important finding was that the boys subjected to the autocratic leader reacted either aggressively or apathetically.

Although whether these studies can be generalized is questionable, they did provide early support for the use of democratic styles of supervision rather than autocratic styles.

The behavioural approach marked the first time that human behaviour in organizations was systematically analyzed. Although the scientific administration movement at the turn of the century recognized the human element of business, scientific administrators did not give as much attention to the systematic analysis of the human element as they did to the physical mechanical aspects of work.

Preadolescent boys overwhelmingly preferred a democratic leader over either an authoritarian or laissez-faire leader. The boys subjected to the autocratic leader reacted either aggressively or apathetically.

Departure from simplistic human relations assumptions are the process theories of work motivation. For example, the equity and expectancy theories of motivation are concerned with the multipliable, dynamic relationships among the inputs and outputs of motivated behaviour. Process theories also recognize the complex nature of motivation and can lead to improved understanding of organizational behaviour.

V -

A Plan for the Organization

The identification of obstacles that may have an effect on the successful accomplishment of key objectives, whether internal or external, presently existing or anticipated, should be included in the analysis of an organization if the risks associated with goals are high or the consequences of failure are serious.

Some organizations have the resources to conduct sophisticated studies to determine the probability of events occurring; others must rely on the experience and know-how built up over several years. Still others rely on gut feel.

Obstacles occur, among other places, in the following areas or situations: new technology; communications; motivation; employee reliability, productivity, or development; delegation of responsibility or authority; individual and/or group conflicts; overlapping of responsibility; national and international economies; competition; company image; regulatory activity or political interference; product liability; lack of materials or sources of materials; lack of working capital; quality problems. **The list is inexhaustible.**

The administrator who needs to concentrate effort on specific objectives may choose the type of organization in which one person or a group of people (functions) works on one major group of objectives or deals with one major set of obstacles such as government regulations.

The more important the objective to the success of the organization, or the higher the risk associated with the obstacles, the more likely it is that the specialized group will report to the top administrator.

The type of structure just described increases the competence of the group in doing one thing, but it reduces flexibility and the opportunity to develop general managers and adds to the likelihood that the organization will become egocentric and develop functionalism. It increases the top administrator's need to coordinate the activities of

the various groups, but reduces the ability of administrators two or three levels down to make decisions.

Organizations should be self-correcting-i.e., once goals are established and effort is directed towards the attainment of those goals, there should be some mechanism that feeds back performance information to the manager, so that corrective action can be taken. The more important self-correction is to the success of the top manager, the more likely it is that the department or section will report to the top manager. Examples of organizational units designed for self-correction are the controller office, quality control groups in production organizations, internal auditors, and in many organizations, the personnel department.

While the functionally specialized groups' role is to see that the work gets done, the control groups make certain that the work is done correctly with minimum involvement by the top manager. **The organization thus can be self-correcting.**

The administrator's who need structured coordination efforts within the organization will design positions or groups to achieve this benefit. The coordination effort may take several routes. At times, an assistant to position is established with specific coordination responsibility.

Task forces or operating committees are other examples of coordinating positions. Often, when the coordination of functions becomes so poor that organization objectives are not being achieved, product divisions or business groups will replace functional departments or sections.

Organizations can be planned to deal with special problems. And special units can be located in the organization structure in a way that will secure management attention. These units are not established to do something, but rather to motivate others to do something.

Among such units one might number the safety department, the affirmative action department, the management development group, or an assistant to type of position. The more important the unit is to the attainment of the organization's objectives the higher it will report in the hierarchy.

Attempts to achieve the benefits of the catalyst positions just described tend to create staff groups. Staff groups are expensive and increase the need for the top manager to become involved as a coordinator in the administration of several functions.

Organization structure can be used to help develop competent people to take over the reins of the company in the future and /or to meet the growth needs of the company. The structuring of the organization for human-resource development often requires a trade-off with another and perhaps more efficient organizational structure.

Recently we have seen the development of the office of the president and chief executive officer or chairman and the growth of group executive positions. These essentially provide more people with top management experience and create needed generalists. The more functional the organization, the more important it becomes to have such positions to insure the development of generalists.

The administrator who stresses the need to reduce costs to their minimum above all else will structure an organization differently than those who seek to emphasize other benefits. Costs must always be considered.

Although specialized departments or coordinating units may greatly aid in the achievement of organization goals, they are expensive. The administrator must consider the cost in time and effort to coordinate and control the work of others. This is an economic consideration and not a span-of-control question. It is an area where a trade-off may have to be made.

When cost is the key objective, jobs are combined so that the fewest people are doing the most work possible; but this approach may be taken at the expense of other potential benefits.

The setting of objectives and identification of obstacles is the first step in organization planning.

The first step in analyzing the effectiveness of an organizations structure is to determine the benefits needed from the structure. This determination should be made for at least two levels of structure. This might be followed by an analysis of the current structure; then, consideration can be given to modifications or total redesign.

The administrator should review each objective and each obstacle and decide whether specialization is needed, and if so, at which level in the organization. Objectives and obstacles that have a high priority will require placement of the units dealing with them at the first level reporting to the administrator. Those with medium priority will usually report two levels down.

A -

How to Present the Organization Plan Effectively

In organization planning there is a special focus on four points:

(1) structure,

(2) span of control,

(3) height, and

(4) breadth.

Emphasis is placed on the division of work into efficient groupings to meet the needs of the organization. Concern is shown for the interrelationships of each group with the other groups, but not nearly as much concern as is typical of the modern theorists. Span of control is a key factor in any organization administrator.

Mathematical formulas have been suggested to determine the optimum span, but there is no firm answer to the question of how many people one person can supervise. To the height and breadth of any organization are key factors that will strongly affect results.

There is much argument over how many levels should exist between the worker on the line (in the case of the manufacturing company) and the chairman of the board (organization height). Advocating only a few levels in height people are faced with the question of organization breadth, which goes back to the question of what constitutes an effective span of control. Another key point is the question of relationships between line and staff, especially the question of whether staff personnel have any authority and/or responsibility in the organization.

- The modern organization theories are concerned with the identification of the strategic parts of the organization-the dependence of the various groups one on the other, the glue or linking process at work in the organization, and the goals sought by the organization and its members. In his view, effectiveness is the result not of structure, but of group interaction and cooperation.
- Effectiveness depends, on the type of market served, production techniques, growth strategies, and the capabilities of organization members, the information processed, and the decisions made. Organization specialists tend to agree on the following major principles:
 - Organizational efficiency tends to increase as the work is directed toward the objectives of the organization.
 - Within limits, the more specialization of work the better.
 - The more an administrator can manage, the less people it takes to get the job done.
 - There must be a clear line of authority from the top to the bottom of any organization.
 - No one should report to more than one supervisor.
 - Areas of responsibility and authority should be stated in writing.
 - Administrators should always be accountable for the actions of subordinates.

- Authority should be delegated as far down in the organization structure as possible.

Span of control, the ability to manage a certain number of people, is determined by the diversity of the jobs to be performed, the dispersion of people performing the jobs, the complexity of the jobs, the volume of work, and the manager's ability to delegate

The location of personnel in widely spread areas lessens an administrator ability to handle large numbers of persons. The number of persons that a manager can teach and aid in achieving objectives determines the span of responsibility.

This becomes an unfixed limit. Organizations are designed to process information. The amount of information an organization receives and the organization ability to process it should affect structure. Any unplanned need for information processing may dictate the creation of special ad hoc groups to handle the situation.

B -

The Administrator Performance

Acknowledging that choices among alternative approaches to planning, job design, communications systems, etc., should take into account organization and human variables seems logical and may appear obvious (though the number of organizations in which illogical choices have been made is large). Not so obvious, however, is the fact that there are logical linkages among the integrative mechanisms themselves.

For example, the choice of a particular approach to planning cannot and should not be made independently of the approach to designing jobs or distributing rewards in the organization. Instead, in an effective administrative system, planning is complemented by job design, which in turn fits logically with the reward system, etc.

Conversely, many problems in modern organizations are directly traceable to inconsistencies among the component parts of the administrative system-approaches in one area simply do not fit with, or even work at cross-purposes to, administrative efforts in other areas. The need for a high-quality fit among the components in an administrative system is well illustrated in the following (real-life) example where the inconsistency between planning and control is glaring.

Top management has a policy that all capital expenditures in excess of a limit, must be approved by a headquarters planning group. The effect of these latter administrative decisions on the motivation of division managers is predictable.

They feel they are being controlled, and they complain that the purchase and/ or refurbishment of operating equipment is so delayed by the corporate review process that they cannot match the innovation rate of their competitors.

Thus, corporate efforts to develop an administrative process in which decentralized divisions adapt rapidly to market changes are being thwarted by control procedures more appropriate to stable environmental conditions and centralized decision.

The role of administration is to integrate a complex set of organization and human variables and that effective integration is most likely to occur when there is a high degree of consistency among the integrative mechanisms chosen by top administrators. Integration, however, is not the ultimate purpose of organizational systems. Organizations are created to serve some hopefully useful social function, and this function is best achieved when the organization is effective (i.e., does the right things), efficient (i.e., does these things right), and satisfies the needs of its members.

The quality of the choices made by administrators in designing their organizations will, of course, have an effect on organizational performance and member satisfaction. And whether these choices serve as a foundation for, or as a barrier to, organizational growth and renewal, is, as indicated earlier, one of the tests of effective administration.

While most administrative groups seek to design high-performing organizations, there is no single administrative system that will guarantee this outcome. While management is constrained by both organization and human variables, its choice of a given system of administration is clearly not dictated. In these situations, administrators are influenced by a final set of variables not yet incorporated into our model. They are influenced by their own theories of how and why people in organizations behave as they do and, therefore, how and why they as administrators ought to behave in a particular fashion.

Within the block assigned to administrator theories, there are three, the **Traditional**, **Human Relations**, and **Human Resources**. While in fact every administrator has his own theory of administration - his own set of concepts which in part guides his behaviour and his choices among alternatives in the areas described above-we believe that most administrator views can be clustered around one of the three models.

Most likely, only infrequently does the practicing administrator desire, or feel compelled, to pause from his ongoing activities and analyze his own theory of administration. And yet every administrator has such a theory which, if more fully explicated, might be of immense value to him as he designs and redesigns his organization.

Although it is not often recognized, even by successful administrators, every manager behaviour and decisions are influenced by his theory of administration (in essence, a theory is an explanation of how and why someone or something behaves as he or it does). For example, the general belief that, left unsupervised, employees will soldier

on the job implies an underlying set of assumptions about people's attitudes toward work and the administrative mechanisms required to obtain productivity.

Were an administrator to sit down and analyze the characteristics of his own organization, he might begin to develop the theory that appears to underlie what he observes. And, as in the example of Organization he might find some logical inconsistencies in this theory of administration. In an effort to make this exercise easier, we offer three alternative administrative models which exhibit a high degree of internal consistency among:

- (1) the assumptions made about human attitudes and behaviour;
- (2) Typical administrative actions developed in accordance with these assumptions; and
- (3) the expected results which are likely to occur if administrators behave as suggested.

No claim is made that any existing administrative system is fully captured by the Traditional, Human Relations, or Human Resources models. However, the essence of a particular system can usually be found to conform closely to one of the three models, and, taken together; the three models cover a broad range of alternative approaches to administration.

C -

Administrator Behaviour Model on Organizations

Effective human-resource management still largely depends on leadership. This highly intangible but extremely important factor can spell the difference between success and failure in any enterprise.

Despite its unquestioned importance, very little is known about leadership. This is not from lack of attention-more has probably been written either directly or indirectly about leadership than any other single management topic.

Through the years the behavioural sciences have also devoted a considerable amount of research effort to leadership traits and dynamics. However, only recently have any real advances been made in understanding, predicting, and controlling the impact of leadership in organizational settings.

System 1 - the exploitative authoritative leader who has no confidence or trust in subordinates. Subordinates do not feel free to discuss things with the leader, and the leader seldom gets ideas of subordinates in solving job problems.

System 2 - the benevolent authoritative leader who has condescending confidence and trust in subordinates. Subordinates do not feel very free to discuss things about the job, but the leader sometimes gets subordinate ideas.

System 3 - the consultative leader who puts substantial but not complete trust in subordinates. Subordinates feel rather free to discuss things, and the leader usually gets their ideas and opinions.

System 4 - the participative group leader who has complete confidence in subordinates. Subordinates feel completely free to discuss the job, and the leader always gets and uses subordinates' ideas and opinions. Through extensive survey research over the years has been found that organizations led by systems 3 and 4 administration are more effective (i.e., are more productive, have lower costs, and have better morale) than organizations led by systems 1 and 2 administration.

Some recent developments on situational and path goal theories of leadership are also making significant contributions to organizational behaviour and human-resource management. It became evident a number of years ago that the Great Man explanation-that leaders were born was totally inadequate. The Zeitgeist explanation - spirit of the times or situational explanation - was much more plausible.

After years of leadership research, was developed a contingency model of leadership effectiveness. In other words, certain leadership styles were contingent upon certain situational variables. The three critical situational determinants identified:

- (1) Leader-member relations;
- (2) Task structure;
- (3) Position power of the leader.

If these situational variables are very favourable or very unfavourable to the leader, then a task-directed style of leadership would be most effective. On the other hand, if these situational variables were only moderately favourable or unfavourable, then a human relations style of leadership would be most effective.

The contingency perspective represented by this model is needed in organizational behaviour as well as for management as a whole application. The model emphasizes that a given style does not have universal applicability.

Just as content theories of motivation proved to be too simplistic and process theories evolved to better explain the complex nature of motivation, so path-goal theories of leadership evolved to explain the complexities of leadership style.

Not only do such theories explain what type of style may be most effective in a given situation but also why it is most effective. The path-goal theory is largely derived from

expectancy motivation concepts and is based on the premise that the leader is the major influence on followers / subordinates work goals, personal goals, and, especially, the paths to goal attainment.

The effective leader is one who clarifies and helps expedite the path to subordinates' goals. The theory is closely tied to motivation in that the leader who facilitates goal attainment will be increasing the expectancies and thus motivation of subordinates.

D -

A Good Administrator must also be a Good Leader

The top manager of an organization can be fairly certain that power problems do exist when there is a great deal of inter-departmental conflict, when the managers of various departments are at war with each other, when there are character assassinations, or when one or more managers consistently overstep their authority or do not exercise it at all.

There are several techniques for analyzing power problems within an organization. Each focuses on decisions making and results. By analyzing the decisions that should be made, the administrator can designate levels of authority, areas in which managers can make decisions on their own, and situations in which they must consult with or receive the approval of others. There two methods of making such designations:

- Critical decision analysis
- Staff-line analysis.

Critical decision analysis identifies the major decisions that need to be made, identifies the role that each involved group should play in the decisions, and resolves any differences that might exist between such groups.

If the administrator believes that a conflict exists between two groups, he should ask each group separately to identify the key decisions that involve it and its role in the decision - making and also the roles of other groups. The groups confront each other with their role definitions in order to resolve their differences, or the manager brings about a solution.

The role of Line and Staff and their authority are traditional power questions. Many line managers believe that line units are charged with the responsibility of achieving the objectives of the organization and of doing the work for which the business exists, while staff groups are traditionally set up to advise and aid the line.

Over time, staff groups have gained considerable power to control and initiate action- they have expert power. Many of their gains have resulted from increased

governmental regulation in areas such as safety, personnel, toxic materials, security, financial reporting, and the proliferation of technology.

The desire of many chief executive officers to have coordination and control groups reporting directly to them also has increased the influence of stall groups. A useful technique to help the staff manager analyze line-staff conflict involves identifying

(1) The 20 or 30 major contributions that the staff department is making to the line organization,

(2) Those contributions it could be making but is not now making, and

(3) Those contributions that the line administration might prefer not be made by the stall group. The degrees of authority, action, and accountability identified can be put into tabular form showing for each major type of organizational unit:

(1) primary responsibility without notice,

(2) primary responsibility with notice,

(3) consultation before action,

(4) joint responsibility.

Once these contributions, real or potential, have been identified, the stall members and the affected line managers are given the opportunity to indicate the extent to which they now receive the contributions and whether they would prefer more or less effort given to the contribution.

Once both groups have indicated their preferences, the group managers can be brought together to resolve any conflicts. **The techniques described above work effectively when analyzing an existing organization.**

They can also be used by the top manager when considering power allocations in a new organization. Power is allocated to members of an organization in many ways. The location of the manager office grants or withholds power by virtue of its desirability or undesirability.

The top administrator granting of easy access to his office is an allocation of power. At least, it is so perceived by those who do not have easy access. The higher the position in the hierarchy, the higher up in the building the office is located.

The higher the grade levels of the job, the larger the office or the number of pictures on the wall. When the chrome water pitcher with two glasses appears on the credenza, the manager knows that he has it made.

Titles are status symbols. Depending on the organization, and sometimes the industry, the title Administrator, Manager, Engineering may be above that of Engineering Manager, or vice versa. The subordinate who plays golf with the boss may have more power than others since he is assumed to be on the inside track: Informal allocation of power takes place in all organizations.

Office protocols were instituted initially for economic and planning reasons, but very quickly they became a power issue. Power, to be truly effective, must be allocated to specific positions. Several alternatives are available to the concerned administrator.

E -

Developing a Personal Administration Style

Power is simply influence. In modern society, the word power often elicits negative feelings; people do not want to feel that they are subservient to any other person or group of people. Power corrupts and absolute power... is an often expressed phrase.

Power is a fact of organizational life. Some positions and people must have influence and authority over others. From the organization planner point of view (i.e., the practicing manager), it is much better to structure the kinds of influence exerted by other members of management than to allow influence to be exercised at will, at times with unwanted and disrupting results.

Major types of power include the following: legitimate, charismatic, coercive, associative, and expert. Legitimate power is the type of power most often resorted to in organizations.

It is confirmed by the organizational hierarchy. The appointment to a managerial position carries with it authority. Within the confines of the organization, the manager may authorize expenditures for a specified amount of money, make certain types of decisions, hire and fire certain people, etc.

An administrator authority is not spelled out specifically; these decisions may not be made adequately. Charismatic power is the power that one has over another by sheer force of personality. Few people have it; it is an important leadership quality. Coercive power is the ability to influence people by force or reward.

The ability to give or hold back a raise or the threat of termination puts an administrator in a position to influence the behaviour of subordinates.

Associative power is the power that is conferred by association with, for example, a uniform or an office. We allow ministers to give us advice that we might not accept from anyone else. We unconsciously follow the orders of firemen at the scene of a fire, although if they were out of uniform we might ignore their dictates.

Expert power rests in the ability to influence others because of recognized knowledge, skill, or understanding of a problem or situation. Professionals are said to have knowledge of authority, and are, in fact, the people who seem to know the most about a situation. It is interesting to observe a meeting of peers.

The leadership of the meeting will tend to fall to the person who is responsible for a particular area or who has expertise in the area under discussion. One of the interesting things about power is that it is given to or conferred upon someone by the people over whom it is being exercised, and often with the expectation of something in return (reciprocity).

In order for administrator A to have any power, there must exist an administrator B. Administrator B in effect confirms the ability of A to have power in return for something worthwhile usually compensation, better working conditions, or more power. One of the ways that a manager can influence the achievement of the organization's objectives is to allocate power to the members of the organization in a structured way. Power is conferred to positions, not to the people who may hold the positions.

By analyzing organization power allocations, the administrator may find that power relationships, not organization structure or the design of jobs, are blocking the achievement of success. In designing a new structure, the manager will want to specify the power relationships that will govern the work in key areas.

F -

Administrator Corporation Behaviour

The administrator role is primarily that of a controller.

Integration of the technical and human subsystems is viewed as a trade-off, with the needs of the technical subsystem being foremost. Human characteristics must be moulded to fit technical requirements, and where they do not, administrators must take corrective action in order to bring people, not structure, into conformity.

If the organization's environment is relatively predictable, if goals and tasks are stable, and if individuals are trained to mesh with predetermined processes and programs, predicts that people will produce up to minimal standards but will not be motivated to perform beyond this level or take corrective actions themselves.

The role of the administrator is expanded to include responsibility for maintenance of the human subsystem. Although still primarily a controller, the administrator recognizes that people are not machines that their needs may be incompatible with the technical subsystem, and that special attention must be paid to keeping people satisfied with their jobs.

If satisfaction is maintained, the Human Relations approach argues, and then the administration can expect employees to comply with the needs of the organization and to produce at acceptable levels.

Under the Human Resources model, the administrator's role is substantially altered and much more challenging.

No longer a controller but a facilitator and developer of the entire socio - technical system, the Human Resources administrator must truly integrate both organization and human variables.

Unlike the traditionalist, who forces the human subsystem to comply with the technical subsystem, or the human relation, who persuades people to cooperate, the Human Resources administrator fully recognizes the possible incompatibility between human and technical needs and searches for ways to reduce it.

This search is not limited to looking for means of increasing human compliance with the technical subsystem-technical variables themselves are targets for change. However, the Human Resources administrator does not have to be a perfect combination of engineer and psychologist. The study of organizational behaviour has, in recent years, been making advances on both the technical and human fronts.

Thus, the Human Resources administrative role is simply the manifestation of current knowledge in the field, and it argues that while the administrator primary function is still problem finding and problem solving, both the problems and how they are approached are substantially different.

That is, moving from one administrative model to another neither removes nor solves administrative problems. Instead, such a movement merely changes the nature of the problems with which the administrator must deal.

The management and organization theorists who were writing in the first half of this century tended to ignore the environment, or at least to hold it constant, as they sought universal principles of administration.

For example, Weber, while aware of some of the dysfunctions of bureaucracy, implied that this form of organization was appropriate for all organizational settings. Similarly, Taylor viewed his principles of Scientific Management as universally applicable and treated environmental demands as fixed in his search for the one best way. It was not until the late 1950 and early 1960 that models were developed portraying the linkages of environment, technology, structure, and process to one another.

Most of these models, however, dealt with only a limited aspect of the entire process of organizational adjustment to the environment and most were content simply to describe these relationships without explaining how they came about.

End of Part I